

An Analytical View of Realistic Aspects in Aravind Adiga's *The White Tiger*

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Abstract:

Since 1947, which marked the year that India attained its political independence, a sizeable portion of the Indian population continues to struggle with a lack of access to some of the most fundamental necessities. Globalization has made the considerable socio-economic gap that is characteristic of modern India, which has evolved beyond the colonial age, even more pronounced. On one end of the scale, there is a demonstration of the existence of highly developed urban areas, efficient metro transportation systems, elevated freeways, and contemporary airports. On the other hand, the opposite side of the spectrum is characterized by an abundance of rural communities. From the famous Indian author, Mulk Raj Anand onward, the condition of the destitute has been a source of inspiration for the creative minds of Indian English writers. In recent years, Aravind Adiga has garnered a large amount of fame as an author, earning him a tremendous amount of respect. Aravind Adiga was awarded the coveted Booker Prize for his novel "The White Tiger." The characters, settings, and narration in the work are intricately linked to Indian tradition and culture, effectively portraying realistic notions that convey the essence of Indian ethos. Presenting these practical ideas in the forefront is the aim of this study.

Keywords. Independence, Globalization, Socio-economic, Realism, and Humour.

European colonial powers pillaged and annexed vast swaths of territory as they spread out over the world for centuries. They conquered a huge swath of the world in the 1900s, annexing areas in Europe, North America, the Caribbean, Ireland, and many others. The English invaded not only the western countries but also the third--world countries, where they did not leave any stone unturned in imposing their culture, norms, and practices. Fortunately, India achieved freedom in 1947, and from then on the era is termed "post-colonial."

As a work of postcolonial literature, *The White Tiger* delves deeply into the complexities of India. While several Indian writers discussed the notion of Indianness in their postcolonial literature, Adiga deserves the highest recognition for his authentic depiction of the postcolonial setting in his novels. Postcolonial India - a nation that has suffered the multiple consequences of globalization, is realistically depicted by modern Indian writer, Aravind Adiga. The author points out to the fact that while many Indians have benefited financially

from globalization, the oppressed people in India's less developed regions have benefited nothing from it.

In many cases, the subalterns are forced to endure factors such as poverty, caste and class discrimination, lack of education, and a dearth of possibilities. When young people from subaltern sections have lived in the city, they develop a sense of ambition and, at times, are willing to resort to any methods necessary to obtain material success. Throughout the novel, Adiga draws inspiration from both his real-life experiences and his imagination, which culminate in his experiment, *The White Tiger*. Balram Halwai is unequivocally the main character in the tale. The narrative progresses as Balram composes a sequence of correspondences directed towards the Premier of China., Wen Jiabo. In the letters, Balram writes about his experiences, which, on a broader point, also talk about India. It is mentioned at the beginning of the novel that Balram is rich and has a high social status. He may have spent his entire life in *Darkness*, but he is now a resident of "Light" and may use any and all facilities available to him. Consequently, he said to Wen Jiabo,

"Your Excellency, please understand that India is two countries in one: an India of light and an India of darkness (14)."

The protagonist's goal in sharing certain details of his life is to give people a taste of the "real" India before they visit.

Balram recounts in his correspondence his experiences throughout his time at school, specifically focusing on the distribution of complimentary meals and clothes by the government. Regrettably, the opportunity is inaccessible to economically disadvantaged pupils. He provides a clear definition of the duty of teachers in ensuring the disappearance of the products provided by the government to the students. Adiga skillfully explores the theme of a corrupt education system, which both Wen Jiabo and the audience comprehend within the framework of post-colonial India.

"But we never saw rotis, or yellow daal, or pickles, and everyone knew why : the school teacher had stolen our lunch money." (33)

"There is no duster in this class; there are chairs; there are no uniforms for the boys. (34)

These paragraphs provide insight into the rationales and strategies for exploiting the government's efforts. Initially, the remuneration for working in the Indian government is not substantial. The concept of exploitation is prevalent throughout these activities. Indirectly, the government exploits the teachers who work in schools, and the teachers themselves exploit the children. The pathetic nature of these illnesses is a representation of India's darker side.

An Area of Darkness by V.S. Naipaul brutally revealed the hypocrisy in Indian culture, the fairy-tale country of Anglo-India, of clubs and sahibs, and *Darkness* is a continuation of that work. (44)

In the story, Adiga explores the economically impoverished condition of Balram's father. Following India's attainment of independence, a sense of optimism prevailed among the populace regarding the potential for positive developments. Regrettably, circumstances took a turn for the worst, leading to deterioration in various aspects. The events that transpired saw individuals engaging in acts of homicide and theft against one another. There was a pervasive lack of adherence to the law. The individuals displayed extreme ferocity, insatiable hunger, devoured all others, and hence had enlarged abdomens.

“To sum up, in the old days there were one thousand castes and destinies in India. These days, there are just two castes: men with big bellies and men with small bellies. And only two destinies: eat or get eaten up. (64).

As a result, there were major changes in society that affected individuals in many ways. As stated by Balram, his father was a victim of deception perpetrated by a member of a different social group, which ultimately led to the loss of his successful business. Due to the fact that he was at a loss, he turned to working as a rickshaw puller in order to make ends meet. To clarify, his entire family was compelled to abandon their socially regarded position. At that time, there were several castes in existence. Adiga argues that India's social structure is today divided into only two castes: the rich and the underprivileged. This provides a realistic depiction of the present condition of India. While the affluent had significant abdominal bulges, the underprivileged, who have not received adequate food, showed reduced abdominal dimensions.

According to Balram, his father was deceived by an individual from a distinct social group; this resulted in his losing his shop. To make ends meet, he did not know what to do, so he has started working as a rickshaw-puller.

Lieutenant Colonel and the author, Nigel Collett argues that Adiga offers a viewpoint on India that examines the country from a grassroots level. The scene is unattractive, with the strong odors of sewage, the remnants of slum living, the presence of skin diseases and decaying teeth that mar the appearance of the impoverished, and the sight of cockroaches flying around their faces as they mumble in their sleep on the streets and concrete floors of their employers' outbuildings. (91)

Adiga is also conducting an investigation of the government's healthcare system. Individuals with little financial resources had a reduced level of healthcare accessibility, resulting in a heightened susceptibility to life-threatening diseases such as TB and jaundice. In contrast, individuals who were financially prosperous had the opportunity to utilize cutting-edge healthcare facilities. The public healthcare system was significantly hindered by corruption. At this time, Wen Jiabo is aware of the report that Balram has compiled regarding the state of public hospitals and is astonished about the corrupted services.

Two little girls came and sat down behind us; both of them had yellow eyes. 'Jaundice. She gave it to me.'

'I did not. You have me, and now we'll both die!'[47-49].

'No, sir... It's skin disease. I've got it here too, behind my ear—see —see all those pink spots?' 'A lot of people have this disease, sir. A lot of poor people.'

'No, sir. The disease of the poor can never get treated. My father had TB and it killed him.' (237)

Adiga is deeply concerned about the increasing disparity in income that he has observed in India, including the country's essential healthcare system. Corruption and other corrupt activities sometimes flourish in understaffed public healthcare organizations. Shortages of vital medical equipment are another problem in the health care system.

It is lamentable to learn that over 50% of the Indian population is unable to afford the exorbitant medical costs owing to insufficient economic means. Despite the intended purpose

of government hospitals to serve the poor, it is paradoxical that the poor are not benefiting from the government's services. The medical staff is providing financial compensation to politicians as a means of safeguarding their employment, which has become an unavoidable issue.

As a result, once they assume the role of government physicians, they lack the commitment to serve with integrity. Working in private healthcare institutions is an option for some who are looking to enhance their income. Consequently, several individuals with limited financial resources have perished as a consequence of this predicament. Even the main character, Balram's father, was afflicted with TB. His lack of access to the required medical treatment ultimately led to his demise from the fatal illness. It is disheartening and intolerable that such occurrences are frequent in Indian society.

Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam states in his book, *India 2020* that he believes the creation of a clean and hygienic environment comes before the need for better nutrition and the inclusion of necessary dietary supplements. The next stages involve medical treatment and routinely scheduled health examinations, along with preventive healthcare programs that include vaccination and immunization. These products should be economically accessible to all individuals in India and consistently obtainable to them. (220)

Books that are successful in the market place, such as *The White Tiger* by Aravind Adiga, an Indian novelist, and *A Fine Balance* by Rohinton Mistry, an Indian-Canadian author, "transmit complicated ideas in the most powerful way," said Denis Rogers, the director of the Brooks World Poverty Institute in Manchester. In this context, we are not advocating that poets should take over the work of finance ministers; rather, we are highlighting the distinctive and significant insights that novelists bring to the table about the history, effect, and results of "development." (Adiga 36).

For the most part, individuals in postwar India are confronted with poverty. Individuals continue to encounter challenges in obtaining satisfactory employment and maintaining their financial stability, even after years of independence. A significant number of individuals are surviving on a meager income due to circumstances beyond their control, while a greater number are unable to do so. Numerous individuals are experiencing discomfort due to the failure to satisfy their most basic requirements. There is insufficient funding to acquire shelter, clothing, water, or sustenance for them. It has come to Adiga's attention that the impoverished seek refuge in the most populous cities of India, where slums are located, as well as beneath

the flowing water bridges and even pipes that are devoid of water. The following is the White Tiger's description of an indigent woman:

‘Oh, she was one of those people.’

‘Who lives under the flyovers and bridges, sir? That’s my guess too.’

‘In that case, will anyone miss her...?’ (165).

The work portrays the theme of chaotic survival for the impoverished, and Adiga effectively utilizes every chance to vividly convey this. The impoverished are unable to pursue their lofty aspirations due to financial constraints.

The poor have little influence over the reproduction of their children. A great number of people who are destitute give their lives in order to achieve success. Despite the fact that Ram Persad is a Muslim youngster in this book, he comes to adopt the identity of a Hindu because he is forced to do so by his family's financial situation. Many individuals who are experiencing economic deprivation engage in the practice of exchanging their votes for monetary compensation from politicians. In postcolonial India, occurrences of this kind serve as evidence of the hidden flaws within the social structure. Individuals who are financially disadvantaged often feel obligated to exchange their votes for monetary compensation from politicians in order to meet their basic requirements. This indicates the presence of the somber aspect of India, characterized by intense suffering and disorder.

Michael Portillo claims that Adiga's book altered his perspective on issues such as "the nature of poverty" and "what is the real " India." The uniqueness of this one was what made it stand out. Many of us were unprepared for the book's exploration of India's shadow side, which it succeeds in doing by tackling weighty social issues like the wealth gap and the hopelessness of India's impoverished (58).

Adiga's adept portrayal of the issues of post-colonial India, such as loss of cohesion, absence of personal identity, poverty, unemployment, class and caste disparities, is commendable.

Many people believed that achieving political independence was the sole accomplishment after years of fighting for freedom. However, it has become clear that this independence lacks both equality and fairness. India is currently a democratic nation with its

own governance and authority. However, it still faces unresolved challenges such as poverty and corruption. Aravind Adiga assumes the responsibility of exposing the negative aspects of India and the corrupt practices of the current system in order to raise awareness among people about the current state of society. Despite India's progress towards positive change and global leadership, Adiga's effort to uncover these flaws deserves appreciation. My intention is to engage in a process of self-examination, which should not be seen as an attack on the country. (The Guardian October 16, 2008).

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